

A fast method to prepare matooke samples for hybrid screening purposes

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

NARL: National Agricultural Research Laboratories

QDA: Quantitative Descriptive Analysis

RTB: Root Tubers and Banana

TPA: Texture Profile Analysis

Abstract

This report details the faster cooking methods for *screening matooke hybrids*. The study was initiated under the RTB (Roots Tubers and Bananas) breeding project to determine a quick method that can be used to produce a *matooke* product whose characteristics are similar to the steamed *matooke* product produced by the conventional method. The specific objectives of the study were to: i) to identify the various methods used in preparation of *matooke*; ii) to determine the optimum cooking time for the different cooking methods identified in preparation of *matooke*; and iii) to evaluate the physical (texture & colour) and sensory properties of *matooke* prepared using the different cooking methods. A desk study was used to obtain different cooking methods used in the preparation of *matooke* and other food products that are available in literature. Five cooking methods were selected including; electric steaming, boiling, pressure cooking (gas and electric), and steaming with perforated saucepans. For each of the methods, *matooke* cooking time was determined in the Food Biosciences and agribusiness program (NARL) laboratory. These methods were then used to obtain a cooked *matooke* product whose physical (texture and colour) and sensory attributes were determined. The cooking methods were then compared to the conventional method through statistical analysis of sensory (by QDA) and physical attributes. Results showed that gas pressure cooking and steaming with perforated pans were more closely associated with the conventional method as they showed no significant differences from the traditional method in terms of yellow colour, and *matooke* aroma. The PCA results also showed significant correlations of those methods with the conventional method. Therefore, gas pressure cooking and steaming with perforated pans could be considerably useful methods in the rapid screening of *matooke* by breeding programs.

Keywords: Matooke, optimum cooking time, sensory, texture, colour

INTRODUCTION

All the landrace species of the East African highland cooking banana (matooke bananas) are susceptible to pests (weevils and nematodes) and diseases (bacterial wilt, Black Sigatoka) among other constraints (Tushemereirwe *et al*, 2001) necessitating their improvement. Currently, the matooke improvement scheme involves the introgression of the female fertile landrace matooke genotypes with resistance genes from wild male parents or their derivatives. The male parents are not edible and often introduce many undesirable traits that affect the culinary quality of the derived hybrids. This presents a challenge of developing hybrids that combine resistance with acceptable consumer qualities.

Matooke banana breeders have to generate thousands of hybrid lines to increase the chances of getting a genotype that combines the desired attributes. However, the current selection process based on sensory taste panels of matooke consumers has big sources of variations and high chances of missing the few genotypes with the right trait combinations. This in turn tremendously increases the time it takes to select an acceptable hybrid and makes it difficult to incorporate the consumer preference feedback into the breeding process. There was, therefore, a dire need to understand drivers of the culinary quality of matooke in order to develop faster tools to accurately screen hybrids with preferred end-user traits. The RTB Food research intervention has identified the driver traits as yellow colour and soft texture of the cooked pulp and protocol for their measurement using instruments developed as medium throughput tools to screen large sets of hybrids (Nowakunda *et al*, 2023, Nowakunda *et al.*, 2024, Khakasa *et al*, 2024).

While studying colour and texture traits in matooke, it was observed that the sensory properties of matooke were better predicted from cooked samples rather than raw samples. Over time, breeders have heavily relied on the traditional steaming method in the sensorial screening of *matooke* genotypes (Nowakunda *et al*, 2019, Akankwasa *et al.*, 2020). However, this process is lengthy and tedious allowing only a few genotypes to be evaluated at a time. In this study, five different cooking methods were evaluated for fast cooking of matooke while keeping the sensorial attributes comparable to the traditional method to enable screening of many genotypes.

1. MAJOR OBJECTIVE

To determine a quick method that can be used to produce a *matooke* product whose characteristics are similar to the steamed *matooke* product produced by the conventional method.

2. SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

1. To identify the various methods used in preparation of *matooke*.
2. Determine the optimum cooking time for the different cooking methods identified in preparation of *matooke*.
3. Evaluate physical (texture & colour) and sensory properties of *matooke* prepared using the different cooking methods.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Review and selection of rapid cooking methods

A desk study was used to obtain different cooking methods used in the preparation of *matooke* and other food products that are available in literature.

Method	Reference
Conventional	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00593
Boiling	https://doi.org/10.1111/ijfs.14769
Gas pressure cooking	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2004.09.010
Electrical pressure cooking	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2004.09.010
Electric steaming	Khnanh et al., 2018, Nakitto et al., 2022
Steaming with perforated pans	Khnanh et al., 2018, Nakitto et al., 2022

3.2. Sample selection

Three cooking banana (*Matooke*) varieties of contrasting characteristics were selected and harvested at maturity based on finger fullness. The bananas selected were among the most, moderately and least preferred varieties based on end-user acceptance (Akankwasa et al., 2020). They included one indigenous (*Kibuzi*), and two hybrid varieties namely M9 and NARITA 24 respectively. The indigenous variety was sourced from farmers in Kawanda and the hybrids were obtained from the fields belonging to National Agricultural Research Laboratories, Kawanda.

3.3. Sample preparation

One mature bunch weighing between 15 and 35 kg of each variety was obtained, peeled and the peeled fingers mixed in order to obtain a homogenous sample. For each of the cooking methods, 3 kg of the peeled fingers were cooked. The *matooke* were cooked until fully prepared, with assessments conducted at five-minute intervals. During each evaluation, visual observations were made to note any color changes, and a fork was employed to assess the progressive softening of the bananas. The *matooke* were considered ready when they achieved softness comparable to that of *matooke* prepared by the conventional method. When ready, the fingers were mashed and simmered amidst observation for further changes and enhancement in sensory quality.

3.4. Cooking time determination

3.4.1. Conventional Steaming method

Preparation of *matooke* samples with the traditional method was adopted from <https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00602>. This method was used as a control to which the selected fast cooking methods were compared.

3.4.2. Pressure cooking

Two different types of pressure cookers were utilized in the preparation of *matooke*: one electric (10 litre capacity pressure cooker- NL-PC-5310) and one traditional gas/ charcoal stove (16 litre capacity Pressure Cooker- RF356PC1) model. In the case of the electric pressure cooker, three kilograms of *matooke* pulp were added directly to the cooker's pan along with one liter of water, then covered with a banana leaf and the lid. The cooking process lasted for 10 minutes, after which the cooked sample was mashed using a wooden stick and allowed to simmer for an additional 10 minutes. For the manual pressure cooker, the peeled *matooke* fingers were bundled in a banana leaf and placed in the cooker with two liters of water, cooking for 15 minutes. The mixture was then mashed by hand and simmered for 5 minutes.

Figure 1: Cooking Matooke by an electric pressure-cooker

Figure 2: Cooking Matooke in a gas pressure cooker

3.4.3. Boiling

Three kilograms of matooke pulp were added to one liter of boiling water in a stainless-steel saucepan, which was then covered with a leaf and a lid. The matooke was cooked on a gas stove for 10 minutes at high heat, followed by an additional 10 minutes at low heat. The readiness of the matooke fingers was assessed by their yellow color and softness when pressed with a fork. The fingers were then

mashed using a mashing stick to create a mold. The saucepan with the matooke mold was placed inside a larger saucepan containing boiling water and simmered for 5 minutes.

Figure 3: Boiling process of matooke in progress

3.4.4. Steaming with electric steamer

Three kilograms of *matooke* pulp were distributed across various steaming racks within an electric steamer (Avinas Three layer; Model: AV-3D) and cooked for a duration of 50 minutes. Each steaming rack was lined with sections of banana leaf. After cooking, the sample was thoroughly mashed using a wooden mashing stick. The mixture was then returned to the racks and allowed to simmer for an additional 10 minutes.

Figure 4: Electric steaming of matooke in progress

3.4.5. Steaming with perforated pans

Three kilograms of peeled matooke fingers were arranged on a perforated tray lined with a banana leaf, and placed within a stainless steel or aluminum kitchen steamer (Hascevhher) with 2 liters of boiling water on a gas stove. The matooke was then covered with a leaf and a secure lid. It was cooked for 20 minutes over high heat, followed by an additional 10 minutes at a lower temperature. Once fully cooked, the samples were mashed in a clean pan and returned to the perforated tray for a simmering period of 10 minutes.

Figure 5: Steaming with perforated pans

Table 1: Cooking time based on the different cooking methods

Method	Weight of peeled fingers (kg)	Amount of water (litres)	Cooking time (minutes)	Mashing time (minutes)	Simmering time (minutes)	Total cooking time (minutes)
Electric pressure cooker	3	1	10	5	5	20
Gas pressure cooker	3	2	15	5	5	25
Boiling	3	1	20	5	10	35
Steaming with saucepan	3	2	35	4	10	49
Electric steamer	3	1	50		0	50
Conventional steaming method	3	-	90	10	30	130

3.5. Quantitative Descriptive Analysis

Sensory evaluation was conducted on the selected indigenous and hybrid cooking bananas. A sensory lexicon specific to *Matooke* was used, and the variety of sensory quality traits was analyzed in the laboratory through quantitative descriptive sensory analysis involving a trained sensory panel (Khakasa et al., 2024). Each sample was assigned a three-digit code, and a tablespoon of the steamed

product was presented to each panelist. Evaluations took place in booths that were equipped with a sink, running water, and adequate lighting. Panelists received an evaluation form, a pencil, and bottled water to cleanse their palates between samples. They rated the intensity of the sensory attributes using a 10-point scale as outlined in the lexicon. The sensory attributes assessed included color homogeneity, firmness, moisture, smoothness, hardness, moldability, stickiness, sweetness, astringency, sourness, and the aroma of Matooke.

3.6. Determination of colour

Cooked matooke colour was determined according to Khakasa et al., 2024 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foohum.2024.100268>)

3.7. Determination of Texture (TPA)

<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00602>

3.8. Statistical Analysis

Data analysis involved the use of One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) in XLSTAT 2024.3.0.1423 to detect significant differences among cooking methods. Principal component analysis was also done using XLSTAT to determine whether correlations existed between the cooking methods, as well as the varieties and the physical and sensory attributes. Tukey's test was used to compare means among treatments and varieties and statistical differences were considered to be significant at $p < 0.05$. All results were expressed as means \pm *SD*.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Cooking time

The cooking time of matooke prepared using various cooking methods are shown in **Figure 6**. It was observed that the electric pressure cooking cooked matooke to readiness for the least time (20 minutes) followed by gas pressure cooking, and boiling. Steaming with perforated pans and electric steaming took the longest time in getting matooke ready, though it was still less than the time taken by the conventional method.

Figure 6: Graph showing cooking time of matooke prepared by various cooking methods

4.2. Physical and sensory properties of matooke prepared using various cooking methods.

The scores of the sensory and physical characteristics assessed are summarized in **Table 2**. In relation to yellow colour, only the gas pressure cooking method had no significant difference from the conventional method. Gas pressure cooking and steaming with perforated pans had no significant difference from the conventional method in relation to matooke aroma. Regarding firmness in hand, hardness in hand and instrumental texture, the electric steaming method was significantly different from all the other methods used. For smoothness in mouth, electric pressure cooking was not significantly different from the conventional method, while regarding homogeneity of colour, only gas pressure cooking was significantly different.

Table 2: Scores of sensory and physical characteristics of the cooked matooke product

Category	Yellowness	Homogeneity of color	Firmness in mouth	Moisture in mouth	Smoothness in mouth	Hardness in hand	Moldability	Stickiness in hand	Sweetness	Astringency	Sourness	Matooke aroma	Instrumental colour (b)	Instrumental texture (N)
Conventional method	6.116 ^a	7.710 ^a	2.696 ^b	6.058 ^a	7.942 ^a	2.565 ^b	7.551 ^a	5.246 ^a	0.449 ^a	0.261 ^a	0.029 ^a	6.551 ^a	21.314 ^a	3.412 ^b
Gas pressure cooker	5.635 ^{ab}	7.192 ^b	2.981 ^{ab}	5.327 ^{ab}	7.231 ^b	3.019 ^b	7.462 ^a	4.673 ^a	0.442 ^a	0.135 ^a	0.019 ^a	5.635 ^{ab}	21.336 ^a	4.034 ^{ab}
Steaming in perforated pans	4.985 ^{bc}	7.833 ^a	2.667 ^b	5.848 ^a	7.197 ^b	2.697 ^b	7.576 ^a	4.561 ^a	0.348 ^a	0.106 ^a	0.045 ^a	5.727 ^{ab}	22.055 ^a	3.946 ^{ab}
Electric pressure cooker	4.469 ^{bcd}	7.837 ^a	2.816 ^{ab}	6.041 ^a	7.367 ^{ab}	2.735 ^b	7.245 ^a	4.020 ^b	0.490 ^a	0.082 ^a	0.000 ^a	5.163 ^b	20.765 ^a	4.249 ^{ab}
Electric steamer	3.596 ^d	7.632 ^{ab}	3.509 ^a	4.737 ^b	5.912 ^c	3.860 ^a	7.807 ^a	2.544 ^c	0.368 ^a	0.123 ^a	0.053 ^a	4.912 ^b	21.414 ^a	4.864 ^a
Boiling	4.352 ^{cd}	7.817 ^a	3.070 ^{ab}	5.592 ^a	7.085 ^b	3.141 ^b	7.746 ^a	3.930 ^b	0.282 ^a	0.070 ^a	0.000 ^a	5.141 ^b	21.426 ^a	4.267 ^{ab}
Pr > F (Model)	<0.001	0.002	0.005	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.161	<0.001	0.675	0.178	0.416	<0.001	0.995	0.05
Significant	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	No

Figure 7: Principal Component Analysis of Cooking methods, and attributes

Among all cooking methods tested, across varieties, steaming with perforated pans had the strongest association with the conventional method followed by gas pressure cooking. Electric steaming was the most discriminated method characterised by hard *matooke* samples. In relation to all varieties, the conventional method was characterised by yellowness, and stickiness in hand followed by *matooke* aroma and smoothness.

Figure 8: Principal Component Analysis of Cooking methods, varieties, and attributes

The first two principal components comprised 79.18% of the total variance; of which F1 and F2 contributed 60.53% and 18.65% respectively. The factor loading of each attribute on the first two PCs as calculated by PCA is presented in Figure 1. The PCA results show that astringency, instrumental hardness, homogeneity of colour contributed the most in explaining the variation at F1 followed by Yellowness, matooke aroma, sweetness, instrumental colour, moisture in mouth, smoothness, and hardness in hand. On F2, stickiness in hand contributed the most in explaining the variation followed by Sourness and mouldability. PCA showed a clear contrast among the three selected varieties as they were distributed into the different quadrants. Amongst all varieties, Electric steaming (cooking with an electric steamer) was the most discriminated cooking method from the conventional method. For Kibuzi variety, Boiling had the strongest correlation with the conventional method followed by steaming with perforated pans and electric pressure cooking; For M9, steaming with perforated pans and gas pressure cooking had the strongest correlation with the conventional method followed by boiling. This could imply that gas pressure cooking and steaming in pots would result in a cooked matooke product with the “tookeness” characteristics.

5. DISCUSSION

The study results reveal that gas pressure cooking and steaming with perforated pans methods were more strongly associated with the conventional method compared to the rest. Significant differences were noted in yellowness, matooke aroma and hardness, which are major attributes that determine choice of matooke varieties by consumers in Uganda (Marimo et al., 2019; Akankwasa et al., 2013). These results could imply that preparation of *matooke* with these two methods could result in an acceptable steamed matooke product with sensory characteristics appealing to consumers such as yellow colour, matooke aroma and softness (Marimo et al., 2019; Akankwasa et al., 2013). Therefore, steaming with perforated pans, and gas pressure cooking could be considered as rapid cooking methods for use in matooke screening. Among all cooking methods tested, electric steaming presents the least probability for obtaining an acceptable *matooke* product.

CONCLUSION

The study aimed to determine a quick method that can be used to produce a *matooke* product whose characteristics are similar to the steamed *matooke* product produced by the conventional method. Gas pressure cooking and steaming with perforated pans could be considered the most suitable rapid cooking methods for the *matooke* screening process.

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